

Light Pollution and Urban Development: A Spatial Analysis of Belgrade Using GIS Tools

Andrijana Stanković¹

DOI:

Abstract: Light pollution is an increasingly significant form of environmental degradation resulting from rapid urbanization and the excessive use of artificial lighting. Although commonly studied within astronomical and ecological research, this phenomenon also has important implications for spatial planning, as it reflects how lighting is integrated into urban areas and how it interacts with patterns of urban development. The aim of this study is to analyze the spatial distribution of light pollution in Belgrade and to explore its relationship with the structure and intensity of urban development. The analysis is based on publicly available maps of night-time light emissions (derived from VIIRS DNB satellite observations) and the use of Geographic Information System (GIS) tools for visualization and spatial interpretation. The study focuses on identifying areas with the highest concentrations of light emissions and examining their correlation with urban structure and transportation corridors. The expected outcomes include a better understanding of the spatial dynamics of light pollution and its potential role in supporting sustainable approaches to urban planning and lighting management.

Keywords: light pollution; urban development; gis; belgrade; spatial planning; sustainable lighting.

Corresponding Author: stankovicandrijana77@gmail.com

¹Faculty of Geography, University of Belgrade, Serbia